

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

QUANTUM MECHANICS AND ENERGY OF THE FUTURE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8092013>*

Choose the most difficult path. But you won't meet any competitors on it.
Charles De Gaulle

Abstract

This article is devoted to the justification of the world's first alternative, renewable, harmless and sustainable energy source, the very use of which is an industry for the processing and destruction of generated waste - recycling, comparable in volume to the entire transport and energy complex. If this source of energy is used, it is possible to stabilize the world at the current level of consumption and implement the idea of sustainable development.

Keywords: nature-like technologies, alternative and sustainable energy source, liquefied plasma, plasma quantum condensate, interatomic interactions, quantum forces of attraction, exchange interaction of electrons.

Quantum physics is the same age as the century. Its formation began with the work of Max Planck, who first introduced the concept of energy quanta carried by photons. The energy and frequency of the latter are proportional to each other, and the coefficient of proportionality $h = 1.05 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J} \cdot \text{s}$ is a world constant called Planck's constant.

The development of quantum theory followed a complicated path and turned out to be dramatic. This is primarily due to the fact that the properties of micro-objects - electrons, atoms, molecules - are very complex and contradictory. Electrons, for example, according to their status in classical physics are defined as point particles with electric charge and mass. But it turned out that electrons also exhibit wave properties, which are found in experiments and lead to the observed patterns of diffraction and interference. Consequently, the qualities of a wave and a material particle as such are inherent in the electron at the same time. Such a combination of contradictory and seemingly mutually exclusive qualities inherent in one micro-object is the essence of the principle of wave-particle duality formulated in quantum physics. Dualism, consistent with the entire system of available data, at the same time makes it difficult to create some kind of visual image of a micro-object. Of course, an analogy arises with a two-faced (and possibly many-faced) mythological creature - like the pagan god Janus - created by the imagination of the ancients. But the fact of the matter is that logic and fantasy also do not seem to get along with each other. The mathematical style of describing quantum objects turns out to be, so to speak, necessary and sufficient. Recourse to visual images turns out to be as difficult as it is unnecessary. Why this happened must be explained by the philosophy of knowledge. But the fact of the matter is that the philosophy of natural science in its present state resembles a classically beautiful heroine from Russian song folklore, who is trying to catch up with a lively troika with a dashing cornet.

For quite a long time, quantum mechanics was

used to describe atoms and molecules containing a relatively small number of particles - electrons and nuclei. With an increase in their number, the purely mathematical difficulties of solving the basic equation of quantum theory, the Schrödinger equation, increased to a very strong extent. These difficulties were largely overcome by applying specially developed methods of perturbation theory (based essentially on an iterative procedure), as well as by using more advanced computational methods. However, individual micro-objects - atoms, molecules, ions, or their small complexes, still remained the central point of the description. It seemed that the extrapolation of already developed calculation methods and their application to more complex atomic and molecular complexes would make it possible in principle to describe such systems as well. However, the implementation of this approach met with fundamental difficulties. In particular, it was not clear why macroscopic objects,

despite the fact that they are formed by a conglomerate of atoms and molecules, they physically behave differently than quantum micro-objects. For them, the classical method of description completely passes. It seemed that macro-objects and micro-objects were separated by a mysterious but impenetrable "curtain", on both sides of which completely different scenarios were played out. Incidentally, this enabled the followers of the so-called instrumental idealism (the philosophical concept of quantum mechanics) to substantiate the thesis that it is impossible to obtain any objective knowledge about the world of electrons, since it is impossible in principle to remove the veil separating "our" world from the microworld. Apparently, with the discovery of lasers, the successes achieved in the development of quantum electronic devices, and also as a result of research into such phenomena as ferromagnetism and superconductivity, the situation has changed radically. What happened? It turned out that a system of atoms or molecules, or a gas enclosed, for example, in a resonator, under certain conditions, functions as a sin-

gle coordinated system, causing a coherent effect of radiation. The parameters inherent in such a macroscopic system contain Planck's constant and, therefore, are essentially quantum: the entire system as a whole is represented as a kind of single molecule. The curtain dividing the "worlds" is removed. The situation is similar in macroscopic samples that exhibit the properties of ferromagnetism, superconductivity (especially high-temperature) and other phenomena. Global quantum forces cover by their influence not separate pairs of atoms or molecules, but the whole sample, in which the influences of a long-range order are simultaneously "switched on".

The central problem of modern physics is the problem of many particles. The difficulty of solving this problem is related to the need to take into account the collective forces acting in systems of a large number of particles. The importance and relevance of obtaining such a solution is due to the fact that it is the long-range order forces that completely determine the structure of condensed media - solids, liquids, dense plasmas. Understanding the mechanism of collective forces will reveal the nature of many relatively recently discovered phenomena (for example, the phenomenon of high-temperature superconductivity) and use these phenomena in technical fields. So it becomes more and more clearly clear that the long-range order forces have an essentially quantum character. The impact exerted by each given atom on the surrounding atoms can be amplified by the principle of an avalanche: the displacement of one of the stones induces the movement of the entire mass of the avalanche, which moves as a whole.

The concept of long-range quantum forces will undoubtedly have a stimulating effect on the development of not only the indicated areas of physics, but also those technical sciences that are directly related to them. Metal physics, physics of defects and strength of materials, physics of polymers and liquid crystals, applied aspects of the physics of phase transformations and magnetism - these are the branches that directly need some unified and a priori approach to describing the fundamental forces acting in condensed media. It is by no means excluded, for example, that the destruction of a material begins with anomalies in the motion of a small group of electrons or atoms, which take on the functions of those "stones" that create the avalanche mentioned above. In general, it is reasonable to approach solid state physics, if we seriously study the problem, only with quantum measures. Sometimes this approach is difficult to implement, but it works for sure.

Let us turn to the consideration of effects associated with the action of long-range order forces of quantum nature in a plasma medium. Plasma (without the admixture of neutral atoms) is a fully ionized gas formed by electrons and positively charged ions. If the concentration of plasma particles is not too high, then the particles are described by Boltzmann statistics - such a plasma is called non-degenerate. Coulomb forces act between particles, which are screened due to dynamic effects: the potential created by an electron or ion falls relatively quickly (exponentially)

with distance from the particle. The characteristic

distance over which this decay takes place is called the screening radius or the Debye radius. Each given particle in the plasma is affected by Coulomb forces only by those particles that are enclosed in a sphere of the specified radius and centered at the location of the particle. This sphere is also called the Debye sphere.

In the absence of interaction between particles, plasma can be thought of as a two-component (electronic and ionic) ideal gas. In the presence of interaction in the equation of state of the gas, corrections appear negative in sign, which decrease both the pressure and the internal energy of the plasma. These corrections are called classical corrections for imperfection. The total energy of the particles, thermal plus the energy of the Coulomb interaction in the Debye spheres, is always positive, since the corrections for non-ideality are relatively small in absolute value: the classical interaction does not give a related state of liquefied plasma (plasma quantum condensate) discovered by the author for the first time in the world - this fundamentally new state of matter, which combines the features of an ordinary liquid (fluidity, surface tension, internal correlations) and ionized plasma in the usual sense. Theoretical concepts of such a state are based on the quantum theory of exchange forces in condensed media [1, 2]. The main feature of such forces is their collective (unpaired) nature, which ultimately determines the long-range order in interatomic interactions. In general, molecular forces, and especially the forces that determine the long-range order, are of a purely quantum nature.

Quantum forces are a natural fact, because experimentally, experimenters dealing with discharges were repeatedly convinced of this. The exchange interaction of electrons under such conditions leads to the attraction of ions to each other, the binding energy of the latter becomes negative. Such states are often spontaneously realized in nature. Quantum forces are due to the successive overlap of electron shells belonging to neighboring atoms or ions. This overlap creates a first order effect with respect to the de Broglie wavelength to the interionic distance. If in substances that are in the usual phase state, overlap also exists, but with increasing distances between atoms it decreases exponentially, then in plasma (since the spectrum of quantum energy states is continuous) the effect of reducing the intensity of shell overlaps with increasing interparticle distances slows down significantly and is described by a power law. As a result, such a pattern of particle interlinking arises, which corresponds to a chain of sequentially overlapping electron clouds, with each of the branches of the chain extending over a distance of the order of the screening radius. On the whole, the chain covers the entire plasma: plasma ions "captured" by this chain are attracted to each other, and a phase transformation of the plasma occurs. The transition to a new state is accompanied by the release of energy equal to the heat of transformation.

At the above concentrations, quantum forces ensure strong adhesion of particles of matter, i.e. create an attraction, and the bond energy between them becomes negative. The fact that the overlap of the electron shells leads to their efficient cohesion is well known from

chemical bond theory. Let us point to the classical Heitler-London theory of molecular forces, in which such forces are found in the calculation of the simplest molecules based on variations. Variational methods in physics are classified as intuitive, a posteriori. Only a theory based on a direct solution of the fundamental equation of quantum theory, the Schrödinger equation, can be consistently heuristic. phase, as well as to predict those properties of this phase that can and should be used by modern engineering and technology [1, 2].

In modern plasma physics, practically all the efforts of researchers are concentrated in the field of high-temperature plasma. In this case, the emphasis is on "hot" thermonuclear fusion, the difficulties of realizing which under terrestrial conditions are well known. At the same time, there are plasma-phase energy sources determined by the collective nature of the interaction of particles, which is most clearly manifested in a fairly dense plasma (with particle density $n = 10^{19} - 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) in the low-temperature region [1]. This plasma turns out to be much simpler than the plasma intended for thermonuclear fusion. One of the ways to obtain such a plasma is compression by a pulsed electric discharge.

At relatively low temperatures, the plasma becomes non-ideal, since the energy of the Coulomb interaction of particles in such a plasma turns out to be comparable with the energy of the thermal background. However, the main feature of such a plasma, and this circumstance is the main one, is that its state is essentially determined by the quantum forces arising in it. In accordance with the usual qualification, the plasma is not degenerate, at the same time, the average interelectronic distance is several times greater than the de Broglie wavelength of thermal electrons, which characterizes the quantization of the system of particles, and the interatomic distance satisfies the following inequality [1, 2]:

$$r < 10\lambda < r_d,$$

those. the shielding radius is an order of magnitude greater than the Debye radius. Similar conditions also arise (often) in gas discharges, but remain unexplored due to uncontrollability and lack of understanding of the processes occurring in them.

Quantum forces create the effect of long-range order forces in plasma, which, as is known, cause phase transformations in matter. With an increase in plasma concentration, the exchange coupling between electron-ion complexes sharply increases, so that *the plasma forms a kind of condensate* in which the degree of ionization is preserved, but at the same time the properties of the phase state inherent in a liquid are manifested - a phase transformation occurs. The latter, as in ordinary phase transitions in substances, is accompanied by the release of energy, which, however, turns out to be much larger than in ordinary phase processes.

The specific energy release (per gram), corresponding to the latent heat of phase transformation, is the following value [1]:

$$E = 10 z^3 e^2 n^{1/3} / m_i, \quad (2)$$

Where $e = -4.8 \cdot 10^{-10}$ cgs is the electron charge, z is the power

ionization of atoms, m_i - ion mass.

Assuming $n = 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, to estimate $z = 2$, $m_i = 2 \cdot 10^{-23} \text{ g}$, we obtain $E_0 = 10^{13} \text{ erg/g} = 1 \text{ MJ/g}$, which exceeds the energy release of the most efficient fuels (except for nuclear materials).

Energy sources of the type under consideration have a number of properties that should lead to special attention to the physical phenomenon considered here:

The energy release is not associated with atomic transformations or chemical reactions, but with the formation of a specific ionized conglomerate, which has the properties inherent in a light liquid, in particular, surface tension, which increases its

It can be assumed that such phase transformations in plasma take place in nature in a low-temperature but relatively dense plasma. Energy jumps of the considered type, accompanied by energy release, are probably observed in the stellar medium, in ionized gas in the inner layers of planets such as Jupiter, and possibly also in terrestrial conditions, for example, in lightning discharges leading to the formation of ball lightning. Simple numerical estimates show that the necessary physical conditions are satisfied in this case.

The binding energy calculated per ion is equal to ten times the value of the quotient of the square of the ion charge and the average interionic distance, if this energy is expressed in ergs. The corresponding specific heat of transition for the substance of ball lightning will be 20 kJ/g, which exactly corresponds to the average statistical value estimated on the basis of processing observational data. If, using special conditions for gas discharges, we increase the average value of the ion charge by several times, then the specific energy release increases by more than an order of magnitude and exceeds the value of the heat of combustion, say, of gasoline (46 kJ/g). The "fuel" obtained on the basis of the use of a quantum phase transition is environmentally friendly - it is not associated with chemical reactions at all, but only leads to the formation of a "liquefied" plasma substance (such as liquid crystals). To receive such

"fuel" suitable industrial waste, dumps. As a result of its "combustion", a substance is formed that exhibits pronounced electrical and magnetic properties that are useful in themselves.

The idea of saving humanity from extinction, expressed by Academician A. V. Kulakov, is the result of his 50 years of research in the field of breakthrough energy technologies, in the theory and practice of collective forces of quantum nature in plasma (for example, non-ideal), liquid, solids, based on applying the exchange theory of perturbations, he created a unified quantum concept of forces, which determines the long-range order in condensed media. Kulakov's idea is of particular value, because allows technologically to cope with the huge volumes of exhaust gases coming from the world industry into the closed lower layer of the atmosphere, and with the extraordinary amount of waste accumulated during the existence of the planet: sludge ponds, mining dumps, waste landfills, etc. - that is everything that destroys the health and immunity of the population, This is possible only through the use of the new only clean energy in the world proposed by the

author - nanoenergy of a new technological order, materializing as fuel all the garbage of the planet - gases and all waste products of human life, processing all the garbage of the planet according to technology developed by Kulakov into heat, electricity, laser radiation and new methane nanomaterials, allowing these to clean the oceans of the earth and the atmosphere from waste and save themselves from poisoning by the waste products of mankind itself and a climate catastrophe. Isn't this the only and last hope for the salvation of mankind from poisoning by the products of the vital activity of mankind itself?

The author predicted and confirmed the existence of a fundamentally new state of matter, combining the properties of liquid and ionized plasma - a fundamentally new, efficient and harmless source of energy, [1-8] the use of which allows reducing environmental pollution with waste. Cleaning up the planet Earth polluted to the limit, in some parts of which gas pollution, slagging, municipal waste exceed all permissible standards, will lead to the creation of a clean (with zero emissions of any gases) climate and an increase in the immune system of the population, which creates the opportunity for people to exist safely. Since the beginning of the 19th century, countries have switched to fuel combustion technologies with the release of heat-accumulating gases into the atmosphere, while the Earth has warmed by now by 1.1 degrees Celsius. Scientists believe that only decisive action to reduce emissions can keep the planet from exceeding 1.5 degrees of warming - a limit beyond which the consequences will become more catastrophic than rising sea levels, extreme weather. Recklessly and illiterately set by scientists, the goal of achieving zero emissions in the United States by 2050, in China by 2060, in India by 2070 on existing technologies is physically unrealistic, spending fantastic funds on this fix-idea of correction, these countries fall into the trap of destruction. In distinguished scientific work <https://www.conservativewoman.co.uk/we-havent-the-materials-money-or-skill-to-achieve-net-zero-this-century-energy-technology-achieving-net-zero-is-unattainable-in-this-century-and-according-to-the-laws-of-fundamental-physics-never-at-all>. Project Syndicate (USA): Our Zero Greenhouse Future INOSMI NEW YORK — "The solution to the man-made climate change problem is finally clear. With rapid advances in carbon-free energy technologies and sustainable food systems, the world could actually end greenhouse gas emissions by mid-century at virtually no additional cost and with enormous safety and health benefits. The main obstacle is inertia: politicians continue to pander to the fossil fuel industry and conventional agriculture, in large part because they either don't know any better or because they are corrupt." The way to achieve a clean climate is to replace existing obsolete technologies with the greatest achievement of mankind - nanotechnologies of a new technological way of life that produces clean energy and cleanses the planet of human waste. But Science News "It is possible to achieve net zero carbon emissions. Here's how", Alexandra Witze 01/27/2023. "Such massive changes will require overcoming a lot of resistance, including from companies that make money on old forms of energy, as

well as politicians, lobbyists" and the scientific mafia. But if society can bring about these changes, it will be one of the greatest achievements of mankind. We will solve the problem we created ourselves and overcome it." However, it is necessary to take into account the opinion of the wisest people on the planet: Ravendra Nath Yasarapu commented on my work: "A beautifully laid out plan of action for energy and waste. But what to do with the primitive human instinct to accumulate, compete, conflict and consume more than a fair share of earthly resources?. What if we are enemies? Maybe read a book about the planet Venus, on which not a single person was saved on Judgment Day, but for the first time, finally, all the poor and the rich united with their favorite slogan "We are together."

The preservation of life on planet Earth is possible only with a change in technological structures: the energy of water, steam, coal, electric energy, hydrocarbons, the beginning of nuclear energy, nuclear energy ...? It is surprising that the carriers of knowledge about new technologies have not previously been persecuted by the scientific elite and the authorities, as if they intuitively

felt that the persecution of the bearers of knowledge usually ends with the Day of Judgment. My research has shown that a new technological order can be created only on the basis of quantum mechanics, a very difficult, complex and great science, subject to a few. It is bad that I am alone in this achievement of the century (quantum mechanics is the hardest science), but the world champion is always alone. But there is still an opportunity to delay the Day of Judgment on planet Earth. Inaction in changing the technological order on planet Earth is unacceptable.

By the way, I ask the editors of the respected "Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science", if possible, to help expedite the presentation of the published (and therefore voted) Nobel Prize in physics in 2016 to me, delayed by the efforts of the Russian "scientist" who forced me to satisfy his unacceptable conditions for sharing my Nobel Prize.

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